

Improvement in Stencil Printing for Solder Paste Process of Semiconductor Device

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I. OVERVIEW

- Surface mount technology (SMT) includes a solder paste printing process wherein the solder paste material is applied below the semiconductor device using stencil printing
- Development of this type of technology applied in a semiconductor leadframe package offers great challenges, especially as the stencil printing is used for the solder ball creation
- A specialized semiconductor leadframe package shown in Fig. 1 with high-density input-output (I/O) connectivity requires the said stencil printing for solder paste process

Fig. 1. Bottom view of the specialized semiconductor leadframe device.

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- During the stencil printing process, one of the issues encountered is the off-centered ball as illustrated in Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Off-centered ball defect appearance.

- Aside from alignment issues due to warpage, one cause of the off-centered ball is the viscosity of the solder paste material
- The solder paste material in Fig. 2 also showed a colder or uncured characteristic
- Though machine parameter optimization was extensively employed, still off-centered balls occur

III. PACKAGE DESIGN SOLUTION AND PROCESS IMPROVEMENT

- As previously mentioned, one factor that contributes to off-centered ball is the type of solder paste material
- Now with the improved design using a new solder paste material with thin viscosity, the solder ball formation greatly improved as highlighted in Fig. 3

Fig. 3. Improved solder ball formation.

- The new solder paste material in Fig. 3 showed cured solder paste appearance, as compared to the material in Fig. 2 with colder solder joints characteristic
- Another advantage of the solution is that the new solder paste material has higher thermal and electrical response compared to the other one